

Abnormal Event Detection in EEG Imaging - Comparing Predictive and Model-based Approaches

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Abstract—The detection of abnormal/unusual events based on dynamically varying spatial data has been of great interest in many real world applications. It is a challenging task to detect abnormal events as they occur rarely and it is very difficult to predict or reconstruct them. Here we address the issue of the detection of propagating phase gradient in the sequence of brain images obtained by EEG arrays. We compare two alternative methods of abnormal event detection. One is based on prediction using a linear dynamical system, while the other is a model-based algorithm using expectation minimization approach. The comparison identifies the pros and cons of the different methods, moreover it helps to develop an integrated and robust algorithm for monitoring cognitive behaviors, with potential applications including brain-computer interfaces (BCI).

I. INTRODUCTION

Abnormal event detection from spatio-temporal data has been of great interest in many real world image processing applications [1]–[3]. In the context of this work, a pattern in the observed data is called *abnormal* or *unusual*, if it occurs rarely and thus it is difficult to predict and reconstruct. Potential areas include emergency response, forensics, and biomedicine [4], [5]. Here we consider the specific biomedical task of EEG image processing. The goal of this work is identifying neural signatures in EEG images, which are indicative of intentional behavior of animals and humans [6], [7].

Studies on EEG signatures include amplitude modulated (AM) and phase modulated (PM) patterns. Amplitude modulation (AM) patterns emerge in response to stimulus and represent the meaning of the signal to the animal in the context of its past experiences. In addition to AM patterns, phase modulation (PM) patterns are studied as well in EEG signals. During the existence of a given AM pattern the phases across the cortex are well synchronized with small phase dispersion across cortical areas. However, AM patterns are metastable and they change from time-to-time, reflecting the changing internal or external state of the animal. During the change from one pattern to the other, significant phase gradients occur, which is manifested in highly variable PM patterns [8], [9].

These observations lead to our present research on detecting changes in phase modulation (PM) patterns. Phase changes are intermittent, happen rapidly, and they can be termed *abnormal event* in the context of this study. One detection approach is based on the observation that phase differences between spatially distributed EEG channels often form concentric

circular patterns, termed *phase cones*. The detection of phase cones is very difficult in the high level of noise and clutter, but some results are quite promising [10]. An alternative approach models the dynamic texture of spatio-temporal data using a predictive dynamical system [11], [12]. It is interesting to compare predictive and evidence-based approaches [13], which is the focus of this work.

This work starts with the description of the applied detection methods, including a (linear) dynamical system and the phase cone-based identification. The linear dynamical system has two components. One for modeling the appearance and the other for modeling the dynamics. The error for each frame is determined by using the sum of reconstruction error and prediction error. This leads to the detection of the abnormal frames as a function of the error. The phase cone approach uses an expectation maximization (EM) algorithm for a mixture model with known component distribution functions (phase cones). We fit the parameters of the cones, including the position of the apex in space and time, and their slope. The comparison of the two approaches shows that they provide complementary views on the observed PM pattern sequences. We conclude with suggestions for future research.

II. DESCRIPTION OF THE APPLIED MODELS

A. Definition of dynamic texture

A dynamic texture [14], [15] is a generative model for both appearance and dynamics of video sequence. The appearance component (vectorized video frame at time t) is encoded by an observed variable y_t and the dynamics (evolution of the video over time) is encoded by a hidden state variable x_t . The variables are related through a linear dynamical system defined by

$$x_t = Ax_{t-1} + v_t \quad (1)$$

$$y_t = Cx_t + w_t + \bar{y} \quad (2)$$

where $x_t \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $y_t \in \mathbb{R}^m$ (typically $n \ll m$).

The parameter $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is a state transition matrix, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ is an observation matrix (e.g. containing the principal components of the video frames) and \bar{y} is the mean of the dynamic

texture. The driving noise process v_t is normally distributed with zero mean and covariance Q , i.e. $v_t \sim N(0, Q)$ where $Q \in S_+^n$ is a positive-definite $n \times n$ matrix. The observation noise w_t is also zero mean and Gaussian, with covariance R , i.e. $w_t \sim N(0, R)$ where $R \in S_+^m$ (typically R is assumed i.i.d., $R = rI_m$). The initial condition is specified by a fixed initial vector $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n$, or equivalently $x_1 \sim N(\mu, Q)$, where $\mu = Ax_0$. The dynamic texture is specified by the parameters $\theta = \{A, Q, C, R, \mu, S, \bar{y}\}$.

B. Learning dynamic texture

A number of methods are available to learn the parameters of the dynamic texture from a training video sequence. Here we have used the procedure proposed in [14], which learns the spatial and temporal parameters of the model separately. Given an observed video sequence (in matrix form), $Y_{1:T} = [y_1 \dots y_T] \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times T}$, the mean is first estimated by the sample mean

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T y_t \quad (3)$$

and the mean-subtracted video sequence $\tilde{Y}_{1:T} = [\tilde{y}_1 \dots \tilde{y}_T]$.

To estimate the model parameters, the video sequence is subject to a principal component analysis (PCA), performed by singular value decomposition (SVD)

$$\tilde{Y}_{1:T} = USV^T \quad (4)$$

The observation matrix is estimated from the n principal components of largest eigenvalue

$$C = [u_1 \dots u_n] \quad (5)$$

where u_i is the i -th column of U , and it was assumed that the diagonal entries of S are ordered by decreasing value. The state-space variables are then estimated with

$$\hat{X}_{1:T} = [\hat{x}_1 \dots \hat{x}_T] = C^T \tilde{Y}_{1:T} \quad (6)$$

leading to the least square estimate of the state-transition matrix [14]

$$A = \hat{X}_{2:T} (\hat{X}_{1:T-1})^\dagger \quad (7)$$

where $X^\dagger = X^T (XX^T)^{-1}$ is the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse of X . The other parameters are calculated using the following equations

$$\hat{V}_{1:T-1} = \hat{X}_{2:T} - A \hat{X}_{1:T-1} \quad (8)$$

$$Q = \frac{1}{T-1} \hat{V}_{1:T-1} (\hat{V}_{1:T-1})^T \quad (9)$$

$$\mu = \hat{x}_1 \quad (10)$$

$$S = Q \quad (11)$$

$$\hat{W}_{1:T} = \tilde{Y}_{1:T} - C \hat{X}_{1:T} \quad (12)$$

$$R = \frac{1}{T} \hat{W}_{1:T} (\hat{W}_{1:T})^T \quad (13)$$

C. Detecting abnormal frames

We can calculate the error of each frame in the video sequence by summing up the reconstruction error and prediction error using the following equation

$$E = \hat{W}_{1:T}^2 + \hat{V}_{1:T}^2 \quad (14)$$

and the frame is considered as abnormal if the error of the corresponding frame crosses a chosen threshold.

D. Mixture model for phase conde detection in frames

The estimation methodology is based on [10]. Given a set of models $p(\cdot|h)$, $h = 1, \dots, H$ that depend on parameters $S = [S_h, h = 1, \dots, H]$, and data inputs $X = [x_n, n = 1, \dots, N]$, the maximum likelihood estimate of the parameters is obtained by maximizing the following objective function:

$$LL(X|S) = \sum_{n=1}^N \log \sum_{h=1}^H r_h p(x_n|h) \quad (15)$$

with r_h denoting the proportion of the h -th model component $p(\cdot|h)$ to the mixture. The algorithm is generic and can work with any number of models H . This approach has a long history of successful applications in the area of target detection and tracking.

In this comparative study, a frame is considered abnormal, if it contains a phase cone. Numerous observations of the ECoG phase patterns lead to the hypothesis that the phase gradient starts at a single point, called apex. Following its initiation, the phase gradient propagates with constant lateral velocity through the cortex, resulting in a cone shaped pattern of phase differences. We assume that the height of the cone at the apex changes linearly with time. The parts of the cortex not affected by the propagating phase gradient of the cone maintain an unchanged phase. Our cone detection method is based on finding the best fit between the data and the mixture of one or several propagating cones.

Here we include results of phase cone detection in EEG image sequences, based on single frame processing. Once the cones are detected in a given frame, we look for cones with closely located apices in nearby frames and chain them together to identify them as instances describing the evolution of a single cone.

III. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A. Data

Electrical activity of rabbit cortices has been measured using an array of 8×8 clinically implanted electrodes [9]. The space between the electrodes is 0.8 mm covering an area of 5.6 mm * 5.6 mm in either of the olfactory, visual, auditory or somatomotory cortices [8]. Here, experiments on the visual cortex are analyzed. Experiments have been conducted for a duration of 6 s, which have been divided into 3 s pre-stimulus and 3 s post-stimulus periods. The sampling frequency was 500 Hz, which gave a total of 3000 sample points for each of the 64 channels. The rabbits were trained to discriminate visual conditioned stimuli eliciting conditioned responses, which have been analyzed during the 3 s post stimulus time segments. During data recording, the signals were low-pass filtered at 100 Hz.

B. Preprocessing EEG data

Preprocessing of the signal is conducted as follows. We start with the raw EEG time series and apply spatial low-pass filtering (across channels) and temporal (across time) band pass filtering. The initial bandwidth is set between 20-80Hz and the entire data set is normalized to unit standard deviation. Then a specific narrow frequency band is selected for detailed Hilbert analysis. Results introduced in this work are based on 26-30 Hz band.

The Hilbert transformation is applied to the data as follows. The signal of each channel is denoted as $v_j(t)$, $j = 1, \dots, n$. The real-valued time series $v_j(t)$ obtained at a trial is transformed to a complex time series $V_j(t)$, with a real part $v_j(t)$ and imaginary part, $u_j(t)$:

$$V_j(t) = v_j(t) + iu_j(t), \quad j = 1, \dots, n. \quad (16)$$

Here the real part is the original time series (Fig. ?? blue curve), while the imaginary part is derived from the Hilbert transform of $v_j(t)$, denoted as $u_j(t)$ (Fig. ?? red curve).

$$u_j(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} P.V. \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{v_j(t')}{t-t'} dt', \quad (17)$$

where P.V. signifies the Cauchy Principal Value. At each digitizing step the EEG yields a point in polar plot in the complex plane. Sequences of steps give a trajectory of the tip of a vector rotating counterclockwise in the complex plane with elapsed time. The vector length at each digitizing step, t , is the analytic amplitude (AA) which is given by the square root of the squares of the imaginary and real parts of the signal:

$$AA_j(t) = \sqrt{(v_j^2(t) + u_j^2(t))}. \quad (18)$$

The angle of the vector with respect to the real axis is the analytic phase (AP):

$$AP_j(t) = \text{atan}\left(\frac{u_j(t)}{v_j(t)}\right), j = 1, \dots, n. \quad (19)$$

Here we focus on the PM patterns formed by the AP determined over the EEG array on the visual cortex of the rabbit.

C. Algorithm of the comparisons

Fig. 1: Schematic view of the comparison methodology showing the EEG array over the rabbit visual cortex, preprocessing, the linear dynamic filter and the cone fit frame-by-frame.

Figure 1 illustrates various components of the proposed comparative algorithm. Data are acquired from the EEG array located on the visual cortex of the rabbit. Each experiment contains 3000 frames at time steps of 2 ms (total duration of the movie is 6000 ms). The movie of the PM patterns is processed either by the linear dynamic system (LDS) or by the phase cone fit algorithm (CFA). Both methods produce a binary map of abnormal events in the movie frames, however, they work on completely different principles. LDS builds a model to predict the frame sequences and marks the anomaly if the discrepancy between prediction and actual data exceeds a threshold. This approach does not make any assumption on the nature of the objects in the images. CFA is a model based approach. It does assume that any event would have the shape of a cone and uses a log likelihood EM algorithm to produce the best fit. At the end, CFA produces a binary map, in which the detected cones are marked as one. Finally, the results of the two methods are compared to make decision of the presence/absence of anomalies.

IV. RESULTS

A. Abnormal event detection by the predictive model

We calculate the analytic signals after Hilbert-transforming the 64-channel ECoG array data like in [9]. Here we have used the movie of PM patterns for detecting abnormal frame instances. We analyzed a total of 39 experiments conducted by the same conditions. Each experiment starts with a 3s resting period, followed by a flash input, and a 3 s post-stimulus period. Figure. 2 shows the detected abnormal frames (marked in white) in all 39 experiments. The algorithm has a sensitivity threshold to declare an event to be an anomaly. Figure. 2a-d shows the effect of changing threshold on the detection. It is clearly seen that higher threshold values produce less frequent declaration of abnormal events.

Fig. 2: Detected abnormal frames, from a total of 39 experiments. (a) threshold = 40, (b) threshold = 50, (c) threshold = 60, (d) threshold = 70.

Fig. 3: Average number of detected abnormal events for the 500 image frames corresponding to the post-stimulus time window between 3 s to 4 s; all 39 experiments are shown; (a) threshold = 40, (b) threshold = 50, (c) threshold = 60, (d) threshold = 70.

To evaluate the role of the threshold, we conduct detailed study of the detection results. It is known that the most important changes in the PM patterns happen in the 1 s following the stimulus. Therefore, we analyze in details the time frames between 3 s and 4 s, which correspond to the immediate post-stimulus interval. Figure. 3 shows the average number of abnormal frames between 3 s to 4 s, from all the 39 experiments. There is a more refined temporal structure seen in the case of smaller thresholds, however, it is difficult to determine which threshold to select based on these data. Studying the phase cone fit algorithm provides some help in this regards.

B. Phase cone detection frame-by-frame

Results of the detection of phase cones is illustrated in Fig. 4a. Note that the phase cone detection algorithm uses data before and after the fitting period, therefore, there are no cones shown in the first and last 0.5 s. The enlarged section with 500 frames in the post-stimulus interval (3s - 4s) is shown in Fig. 4b. Fig. 4c-d display the total number of detected cones in during the whole length of the experiment and for the 1s post-stimulus period, respectively.

Fig. 4: Schematic view of the comparison methodology showing the EEG array over the rabbit visual cortex, preprocessing, the linear dynamic filter and the cone fit frame-by-frame. The horizontal axis shows the frame sequence number, i.e., in (a) and (c) 0 - 3000 (whole duration), in (b) and (d) from 1500 - 2000 (post-stimulus period). the vertical axis in (a) and (b) is the experiment number running from 1 to 39; the vertical axis in (c) and (d) shows the number of experiments with cones detected at that instant.

It is difficult to make definite conclusions based on at the present analysis. However, some interesting observations can be made, especially regarding the post-stimulus interval. Fig. 4b indicates less white dots in the time period 1500-1600

frames (3s - 3.2 s) immediately following the stimulus, suggesting that there would be less phase cones. This conclusion is confirmed by Fig. 4d, where the total number of detected cones are shown for all 39 experiments. One can see values oscillating between 0 and 4. During frames 1600 - 1800 (3.2 s - 3.4 s), on the other hand, we observe drastically increased cone activity. This result is in line with previous findings [10]. Moreover, it can be interpreted in terms of the cognitive cycle [9].

C. Discussions

In the case of EEG data, no independent "ground truth" can be declared on the presence and/or absence of abnormal events/phase cones. Thus the different methods cannot be evaluated based on any independent external judgement. Instead, we look at the consistency of the results. In order to compare linear dynamic system (LDS) and phase cone fit algorithm (CFA) in EEG analysis, first we study their sensitivity.

Fig. 5 shows the proportion of the segments with events/cones at each experiment for LDS (circles) and CFA (stars), while crosses indicate the occurrence of events by both methods simultaneously. There is a clear correlation between the results obtained by the different approaches, although the actual values differ significantly. As a general trend, LDS is more sensitive than CFA, i.e., the curve for LDS runs higher than CFA. To support this statement qualitatively, we calculate the average proportion of instances declared as qualifying events by the various approaches. In average, LDS identifies 0.202 (20.2% part of all events as abnormal. The same quantity is 0.095 (9.5%) for CFA, and 0.061 (6.1%) for the combined LDS+CFA approach. Based on these results, several important conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) About 2/3-rd (0.061/0.095) of the CFA detections are picked up by the LDS method. This is a reasonably good agreement, considering that these two methods are based on completely different operational principles.
- 2) LDS is more sensitive detection method than CFA, i.e., it detect about twice as much abnormal events (0.202/0.095). By adjusting the sensitivity threshold of LDS, a better match between the methods may be achieved. However, this is not the focus of the present study.
- 3) The fact that LDS detects more events may be due to the fact that it treats the events (cones) as they evolve, so it may detect an event based on interpolation between qualifying time point, although the given intermediate point may not qualify, e.g., based on the frame-by-frame CFA. Fig. 6 shows that this is indeed the case in some instances, at least.

Figure 6 shows a detailed analysis of the post-stimulus frames (1500-2000) for a specific experiment (no. 27). The vertical axis denotes the index of the method as follows: '1' stands for LDS, '2' shows CFA, and '3' shows combined LDS+CFA. Obviously, the combined LDS+CFA index is a subset of any of the other two. In addition, the combined detection at around frame 1620 is preceded by short detection periods in the LDS method. This example may indicate that indeed, LDS can detect actual abnormal events earlier than CFA.

Finally, the example at around frames 1780-1860 shows that LDS indeed "interpolates" the abnormal events for intermediate time point, while CFA sees only fragmented cone occurrences. These results are very interesting and may provide deep insight into the dynamical processes taking place in the cortex during higher cognitive processing.

Fig. 5: Proportion of of qualified events according to various detection algorithms, in the average sense; circles (o): LDS, stars (*): CFA, crosses (+): detection by LDS and CFA, simultaneously.

Fig. 6: Proportion of of qualified events according to various detection algorithms, in the average sense; circles (o): LDS, stars (*): CFA, crosses (+): detection by LDS and CFA, simultaneously.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Recent experiments with high-resolution EEG imaging indicate that brain processes information as a cinema in consecutive frames. It is of great interest to extract meaning from the frames as they follow each other while the subject processes sensory information. The theoretical work has important impact on a wide-range of application areas. Specifically, results of these study can be implemented in improved brain-computer interfaces, with potential applications for supporting the elderly and people with disabilities, and the development of personal assistants for fitness and relaxation training, among other areas.

In this work, EEG data from rabbits are analyzed with a focus on phase modulation (PM) patterns and associated propagating phase cones. We employed and compared two detection methods. As the employed datasets are relatively small, our conclusions are tentative:

- The first algorithm is based on a linear dynamical system, using principles of advanced video processing.

The second approach uses a pattern identification (phase cone detection) algorithm.

- Comparison of the two approaches shows that they provide complementary views on the observed PM sequences, and their combination could produce improved algorithms for BCI designs.

Further elaboration of the preliminary results introduced here is expected to provide deep insight into the dynamical processes taking place in the cortex during higher cognitive processing.

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REFERENCES

- [1] B. Efron, T. Hastie, I. Johnstone, and R. Tibshirani, "Least angle regression," *Annals of Statistics*, vol. 32, pp. 407–499, 2004.
- [2] M. Aharon, M. Elad, and A. Bruckstein, "K-SVD: An Algorithm for Designing Overcomplete Dictionaries for Sparse Representation," *Signal Processing, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 54, no. 11, pp. 4311–4322, Nov. 2006. [Online]. Available: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/TSP.2006.8811199>
- [3] A. Coates and A. Y. Ng, "Learning feature representations with k-means," in *In Neural Networks: Tricks of the Trade, Reloaded*. Springer LNCS, 2012.
- [4] J. Xu, S. Denman, S. Sridharan, C. Fookes, and R. Rana, "Dynamic texture reconstruction from sparse codes for unusual event detection in crowded scenes," in *Proceedings of the 2011 joint ACM workshop on Modeling and representing events*, pp. 25–30, 2011.
- [5] O. Popoola and K. Wang, "Video-based abnormal human behavior recognition: a review," *Systems, Man, and Cybernetics, Part C: Applications and Reviews, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 42(6), pp. 865–878, 2012.
- [6] J. H. v. Hateren and A. v. d. Schaaf, "Independent component filters of natural images compared with simple cells in primary visual cortex," *Proceedings: Biological Sciences*, vol. 265, no. 1394, pp. 359–366, Mar 1998.
- [7] M. Bar, "Top-down facilitation of visual recognition," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, vol. 103(2), pp. 449–454, 2006.
- [8] J. Barrie, W. Freeman, and M. Lenhart, "Modulation by discriminative training of spatial patterns of gamma eeg amplitude and phase in neocortex of rabbits," *Journal of neurophysiology*, vol. 76, no. 520-539, p. 36, 1996.
- [9] R. Kozma, J. J. Davis, and W. J. Freeman, "Synchronized minima in ecog power at frequencies between beta-gamma oscillations disclose cortical singularities in cognition," *Journal of Neuroscience and Neuroengineering*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 13–23, 2012.
- [10] R. Kozma and R. Ilin, "Detection of spatiotemporal phase patterns in ecog using adaptive mixture models," *Proc. IEEE/INNS Int. Conf. Neur. Networks IJCNN2013*, pp. 1290–1296, 2013.
- [11] B. Banerjee and J. Dutta, "Efficient learning from explanation of prediction errors in streaming data," in *Big Data, 2013 IEEE International Conference on*, pp. 14–20, 2013.
- [12] —, "Selp: A general-purpose framework for learning the norms from saliencies in spatiotemporal data," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 138, pp. 41–60, 2014.
- [13] G. Hesselmann, S. Sadaghiani, K. J. Friston, and A. Klein-Schmidt, "Predictive coding or evidence accumulation? false inference and neuronal fluctuations," *PLoS ONE*, vol. 5(3), p. e9926, 2010.
- [14] G. Doretto, A. Chiuso, Y. N. Wu, and S. Soatto, "Dynamic textures," *International Journal of Computer Vision*, vol. 51, no. 2, pp. 91–109, 2003.
- [15] A. B. Chan and N. Adviser-Vasconcelos, *Beyond dynamic textures: a family of stochastic dynamical models for video with applications to computer vision*. University of California at San Diego, 2008.